

WayOut Project

Integrated Exit Programme for Prison and Probation – WayOut

Project Number: 823690

SFP-2017-AG-RAD

D3.3 - Evaluation framework user manual

Version Def

29th May 2020

Change Control

Document Properties

Deliverable No.	3.3		
Work Package No	3	Work Package Title	Evaluation framework of exit programmes
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Official deliverable name	Evaluation framework user manual		
Date	29-05-2020		
Dissemination Level	Public		

Revision History

Version	Date	Comments
2.1	15/04/2020	This second version of the document incorporates feedback received from partners both in written format and during the fourth project meeting.
2.2	26/05/2020	Incorporates partners' feedback to the to the previous version.
Def	29-05-2020	Review of the deliverable

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Executive summary

The current deliverable presents and evaluation framework user manual. Following the previous work that was developed, namely the literature review on exit strategies (D3.1) and the evaluation framework report (D3.2), it provides project partners with a framework to implement the evaluation of identified exit programmes. Moreover, it guides partners on the analysis of data collected from both the online questionnaires and the interviews phases.

1. Introduction

The current deliverable is an internal document aimed at providing guidelines for the partnership to proceed with the evaluation of exit programmes.

Built upon previous work, namely the literature review on exit strategies (D3.1), and the “Exit interventions evaluation framework report” (D3.2), the current deliverable provides methodological guidelines for the successful implementation of the evaluation framework by different professionals. Moreover, it gives readers instructions on the analysis of the data collected during the evaluation process in order to standardize procedures and improve the evaluation results.

The deliverable structure goes as follows: section 2 presents the method for the implementation of the evaluation techniques, incorporating two sub-sections; sub-section 2.1 provides steps for the quantitative data analysis from the online questionnaire; sub-section 2.2 provides methodological guidance on the analysis of data that comes from the interviews; section 3 presents the conclusions from the current deliverable. Annexes were also developed to provide partners with useful templates for the evaluation process.

2. Implementation of the evaluation techniques.

The evaluation framework report considers the implementation of the following data collection methods: online questionnaire and interview.

Before the implementation of the evaluation framework, partners need to engage with potential respondents. Therefore, after mapping the existing Exit programmes (cf. Deliverable 3.4), the contact person identified in the document should be contacted with the available means (e.g., e-mail; LinkedIn profile). Templates for the communication to be sent can be found on Deliverable 3.5.

Regarding the online questionnaire, a questionnaire targeting programme managers and/or other members of the implementation team was developed. Questionnaire encompasses items linked with the identified attributes we aim to evaluate. Potential questionnaire respondents should be flagged during first contact with the contact person identified in Deliverable 3.4. Contact with potential respondents should be made, initially, by phone call, e-mail, or through their social media professional profiles (e.g., LinkedIn). After being informed on the goals of the online evaluation questionnaire, link to the final questionnaire should be sent by e-mail. If no answer is recorded during a one-week period, a first reminder should be sent.

Regarding the interview, a semi-structured interview was developed, meaning that partners running the interview should follow the interview script but are allowed to do small changes when needed. Allowed changes include:

- Changes in questions' order;
- Skipping questions (in case the interviewer considers it was already answered);
- Adding questions or sub-questions, if some aspects of the answer need further exploration/explanation.

Conditions for running the interview¹:

Face-to-face interview: in the case of a face-to-face interview, the interviewer should be accompanied by writing material and a recording device. The interview should be done in a proper meeting room, minimising the chances of unwanted noises, interruption or any other disturbances that may hinder the natural flow of the interview.

Online Interview: in the case of an online interview, the interviewer and the interviewee should agree on a platform that allows proper communication with audio and video. The platform should allow the recording of the interview. Both interviewer and interviewee should look for a quiet room in which the call can be done.

The interview should start with a *preliminary stage* where presentation of the interview goals (reinforcing information that was previously sent when the person was invited for the interview) is done and explanation on how the information derived from the interview will be used is provided². An informed consent should be obtained in order to record the interview and use it for research purposes. Independently of the fact that the interviewee allows the recording of the interview (or not), the interviewer should take notes along the interview and must inform the interviewee about that during this pre-interview stage. As an alternative to the recording of the interview, the interviewer will use notes taken during the interview to compile relevant information from the interview that will be then shared with the interviewee for potential completion/correction.

The interview should then proceed, following the developed structure. During the interview, some good practices should apply, such as:

- Avoiding “Why” questions, that are known to raise respondent’s defensiveness.
- Active listening - interviewer should employ active listening skills, providing adequate feedback to the interviewee and reformulating sentences whenever clarification is needed (or to validate the correct understanding of what was said). Considering the sensitiveness of some topics addressed in the interview, active listening is particularly needed to avoid misunderstandings.

Closure of the interview should be done, asking participants if they want to add something to what was previously said, clarifying any doubts that may have been raised during the interview and asking participants for other potential participants in the exit programme evaluation process.

¹ These conditions apply both for the programme managers and stakeholders’ interview.

² Participants should be informed that extracted/selected information from the interviews will be used and compiled in a peer review report that will evaluate existing interventions and provide guidelines on lessons learned and “what works”. This report (D. 3.5) will only be shared between project partners as stated in the project application. However, highlights with anonymised data can be shared during dissemination actions involving project stakeholders.

2.1. Evaluation of exit programmes - analysis of online questionnaires

The analysis of the online questionnaires should be made with the use of statistical software. Descriptive statistics and frequencies should be done in order to produce mean values for each item and the evaluation dimensions. An excel spreadsheet was developed to register participants answers. Since this stage precedes the interviews, based on the overall score and on partial scores for each dimension, partners can adjust their interview questions, searching for additional data regarding some of the evaluation attributes or reducing the importance of other attributes that may have been clarified with the online questionnaire. Majority of items are scored on a Likert-type scale ranging from 1 to 6 (from “strongly disagree” to “strongly agree”). However, some items are scored on a different scale (from “never” to “very frequently”). 1 item score needs to be reversed (“Design of the intervention programme can be improved”). An average score higher than 4 reflects a programme that needs minor adjustments. Overall, an average score below 4 might indicate that the programme needs some adjustments. In these cases, average scores for each dimension should be considered to guide the structure of the semi-structured interview, that is, interviewers should use results from the online questionnaire to improve the interview design. Items related with the contact approach, ideology and programme characteristics will not be considered for quantitative analysis since these programmes attributed do not represent good or bad programme characteristics *per se*, therefore needing a more profound understanding from the qualitative interviews’ analysis.

2.2. Evaluation of exit programmes – Thematic analysis of the interviews

After running the interviews, partners will transcribe the interviews and do a thematic analysis. Transcription of the interview, while being time consuming, represents a first step in order for the researcher to familiarize him/herself with the data, therefore representing an important step to the data analysis technique that should be employed for the analysis of the interviews, that is, thematic analysis³.

Thematic analysis can be defined as “a method for identifying, analysing and reporting patterns (themes) within data” (Braun & Clarke, 2006, p. 79).

Themes should be considered taking into account their relevance for the research question. Prevalence of a theme (in terms of frequency of appearance) does not necessarily mean that it is relevant. The research question this evaluation process aims to answer is “what factors contribute to the effectiveness of exit programmes and how to further improve these interventions in order to decrease the prevalence of radicalisation and violent extremism in our societies?”.

The following steps should be carried out:

1. Familiarize yourself with your data: during this first step, notes can be taken considering initial ideas that came while reading or re-reading the data.
2. Assign preliminary codes to the data: in this stage, the researcher should identify

³ Although we advise partners to transcribe the interviews, each partner should see if this is the best option for them to be more familiar with the data.

- interesting features in the data, assigning a label to those interesting features (i.e., coding)⁴.
3. Search, across the different interviews, for patterns that can generate potential themes: during this stage, the researcher already coded all interviews' data and therefore can start aggregating codes in broader concepts (i.e., themes). The use of a mind map diagram can be useful during this stage.
 4. Review themes: during this stage, a revision of the themes should be done. New themes can be created, as a result of previously separated themes that might now collapse to form a new one. Other themes can have few codes to support their existence and might be erased or, on the other hand, need to be divided in more precise themes when slightly different codes can be assigned to them.
 5. Define and name themes: after finishing the thematic map, names should be given to themes, reflecting the essence of that data set.
 6. Produce your report/deliverable: steps taken during the thematic analysis now need to be written in a convincing way, reinforcing the validity of the analysis. The report should take into account the target groups, adopting a format that increases the likelihood of being read and emphasising the key information.

Steps 1 and 2 can be done by each partner that is doing the interviews. However, from step 3 onwards, leading partner of the deliverable should combine data from the different interviews, sharing its thoughts on potential themes with contributing partners. The incorporation of the different data gathered from the programmes that will be evaluated will allow us to reach broader themes that will be the result of our programmes' evaluation allowing partners to understand “what factors contribute to the effectiveness of exit programmes and how to further improve these interventions in order to decrease the prevalence of radicalisation and violent extremism in our societies?”.

3. Conclusions

Evaluating different exit programmes, with a focus on the European context is a challenging task that this project aims at doing. The current deliverable represents an attempt to operationalise an evaluation strategy that can be feasible and that will allow partners to understand what factors contribute to the effectiveness of exit programmes, compiling information about them and understanding how to further improve these interventions, therefore decrease the prevalence of radicalisation and violent extremism in our societies. Considering the needed steps after the implementation of the evaluation framework that was designed, the current deliverable provides partners with guidelines for the analysis of data gathered during online questionnaires and interviews as well as templates for recording data.

⁴ Here, deductive coding is also a possibility (i.e., assigning data features to pre-existing codes), since questions target specific dimensions of the Exit programme that we want to explore. Therefore, a template is provided to researchers in order to facilitate this step (see appendix 1). For more information regarding the hybrid process of inductive and deductive thematic analysis, please see Fereday and Muir-Cochrane (2006).

4. Bibliography

- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3, 77-101. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1460-2466.1978.tb01621.x>
- Fereday, J., & Muir-Cochrane, E. (2006). Demonstrating Rigor Using Thematic Analysis: A Hybrid Approach of Inductive and Deductive Coding and Theme Development. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 5(1), 80-92. <https://doi.org/10.1177/160940690600500107>

5. Annexes

5.1. Annex I - Interview questions targeted at EPs/ESs manager/head of implementation team. Interview Script

Semi-structured interview questions:

First stage - know more about the programme

1. How would you describe the Exit programme you are managing/implementing/working on?
2. Who is running the programme (organisation)? For how long? How was the programme initially funded?
3. Which institution (governmental / non-governmental) is funding the programme?
4. What identified needs led to the creation of the programme?
 - a. Who was responsible for the design of the programme?
 - b. Was the programme design based on theoretical models in the field of deradicalisation?
5. What skills one needs to have to be part of the team implementing this programme? What kind of skills do you search for in potential team members?
6. Who is implementing the programme (team)?
7. Do you use any kind of proactive communication strategy in order to reach potential participants in the intervention programme?
8. (independently of the contact approach)) To what extent is the participation in the programme voluntary?
9. Does the programme have an ideological component? That is, does it target inmates/probationers' ideology?
10. How long does the programme takes from start to finish?
11. Is the programme implemented on an individual or group level?
12. Do you work with participants' families and social networks?
13. How does your organisation collaborate with different agencies (e.g., law enforcement) for increasing the success of the intervention?
14. How does your organisation protect participants' data when collaborating with other agencies?

15. How are inmates' risks assessed at intake and during the programme?
 - a. Is there any specific risk assessment/instrument/tool under implementation?
 - b. How frequently is the assessment done?
 - c. What is done with the results of the risks assessment?
 - d. If no risk assessment is currently being conducted, do you expect this to change in the (near) future?
16. How are inmates' needs assessed at intake and during the programme?
 - a. Is there any specific needs assessment/instrument/tool under implementation?
 - b. How frequently is the assessment done?
 - c. What is done with the results of the needs assessment?
 - d. If no needs assessment is currently being conducted, do you expect this to change in the (near) future?
17. Do you apply any post-intervention/programme monitoring? If yes, when does the monitoring of participant's ends? Do you run a follow-up of the programme participants? How often?
18. To what extent are other organisations involved in aftercare / are other organisations taking over after the exit programme?
19. How do you ensure the right amount of information sharing with key actors/stakeholders (e.g., governmental bodies; NGOs; participants' family, friends and social networks)? How do you avoid the sharing of irrelevant/confidential information regarding the programme? Does the programme has a plan for crisis communication?

Second stage - programme evaluation

1. How do you measure the level of success of the programme?
2. Why was the intervention considered effective/ineffective? (e.g., the dynamic between the facilitator and the participants);
3. What is the impact of the evaluation on project funding and project continuity?
4. Did your organisation assess the cost-effectiveness of the programme? And if so, how has this been assessed?
5. Were evaluation results used to fine-tuning the programme? Is the programme reviewed according to updated scientific research?
6. Do you have any publicly available evaluation reports?
7. Would you like to add something to what was previously said?
8. Do you have any doubts, comments or suggestions?
9. Would you recommend us another person to be involved in a similar interview? Can you bring us into contact with a programme stakeholder?

5.2. Annex II - Interview questions targeted at stakeholders

First stage - know more about the programme

1. Can you please explain what your role and the role of your organisation in the programme implementation is?
2. To what extent are the programme's interventions adjusted to the specific needs of your country (or region) and the needs of the target group?
3. To what extent was the implementation team qualified?
4. Are you/your organisation involved in the communication strategy to reach potential participants to the intervention programme?
5. Are participants being reached as intended?
6. To what extent was the ideological approach of the programme crucial during the selection process?
7. Do you consider the duration of the programme appropriate?
8. How are inmates' risks and needs assessed?
9. Is there any specific risk assessment/instrument/tool under implementation?
10. How frequently is the assessment done?
11. If no risk assessment is currently being conducted, do you expect this to change in the (near) future?
12. Are you aware of how post-intervention programme monitoring will occur (if there is one)?
13. Are you aware of how participants are followed-up? Is there a plan for aftercare?

Second stage - programme evaluation

1. To what extent is the programme achieving the intended outcomes, in the short, medium and long term?
2. To what extent is the programme producing worthwhile results (outputs, outcomes) and/or meeting each of its objectives?
3. To what extent does the programme address an identified need?
4. How well does the programme align with government and agency priorities?
5. What has been the ratio of costs to benefits?
6. Has the intervention been cost-effective (compared to alternatives)?
7. Is the programme the best use of resources?
8. Do the outcomes of the programme represent value for money?

9. To what extent is the relationship between inputs and outputs timely, cost-effective and to expected standards?
10. How did you justify the need to implement this programme, as a priority?
11. Were evaluation results used to fine-tuning the programme? Is the programme reviewed according to updated scientific research?
12. Did the programme produce or contribute to the intended outcomes in the short, medium and long term?
13. What unintended outcomes (positive and negative) were produced?
14. To what extent can changes be attributed to the programme?
15. What were the features of the programme and context that made a difference?
16. What was the influence of other factors?
17. What has been done in an innovative way?
18. How satisfied are programme clients?

5.3. Annex III - Online questionnaire

How do you describe your exit programme? (select as applicable):

As a Taylor-made intervention

As a cognitive skills programme

As a psychosocial intervention

As an education course

As a vocational skill training

As a set of creative, cultural and recreational activities

Other:

Does the programme considers the involvement of (select as applicable):

Participant's family and social networks

Religious experts

Victims

Former violent extremists

Influential personalities

Other:

[multiple choice question] How would you describe your organisation?

- Non-governmental organisation;
- Company;
- Governmental organisation;
- Other organisation.

Item	1 - Strongly Disagree	2 - Disagree	3 - Slightly Disagree	4 - Slightly Agree	5 - Agree	6 - Strongly Agree
Design of the intervention programme can be improved.						
Design of the programme took into consideration up-to-date scientific literature.						
The implementation team is comprised of skilled professionals.						
The implementation team is multidisciplinary.						
A proactive communication strategy to reach potential participants is put in place.						
Participation in the programme is voluntary.						
The programme has a strong ideological component.						
Duration of the intervention programme is appropriate.						
The programme is implemented on						

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an individual basis.						
There is a strong collaboration between our organisation and other agencies (police, prison, community organisations, etc.).						
Tools are used to assess participants needs.						
Tools are used to draw an individual intervention plan to address participants’ needs.						
Tools are used to assess participants risk level.						
Tools are used to draw and individual intervention plan addressing participants risks.						
Post-intervention monitorisation actions are implemented.						
Former participants are followed-up.						
The programme is connected to a long-term aftercare plan.						
A clear evaluation framework is implemented to assess the programme.						
Participants are involved in the programme’s evaluation.						
Stakeholders (e.g., governmental bodies; NGOs; participants’ family, friends and social networks) are involved in the programme’s evaluation.						
Programme effectiveness mechanisms are being accessed.						
Evaluation results are used for decisions on project funding.						
Evaluation results are used for decisions on project continuity.						
Cost-effectiveness of the intervention is assessed.						
Item	1 - Never	2 - Very Rarely	3 - Rarely	4 - Occasionally	5 - Frequently	6 - Very Frequently
The intervention programme is fine-tuned.						
The intervention programme is fine-tuned with inputs from the programme evaluation.						
The intervention programme is fine-tuned according to new theoretical developments.						
Item	1 - Strongly Disagree	2 - Disagree	3 - Slightly Disagree	4 - Slightly Agree	5 - Agree	6 - Strongly Agree
Programme evaluation reports are						

produced and available to national authorities.						
Programme evaluation reports are produced and publicly available.						

5.4. Annex IV - Template for coding interviews' data

Qualitative analysis of the interviews:

Codes	Data features
Researchers can add lines with their own codes.	
Type of Intervention	
Actor	
Design and conceptualisation	
Team	
Contact approach	
Type of participation	
Role of ideology	
Duration	
Programme characteristics	
Multi-agency approach / collaboration	
Risk and needs assessment	
Monitorisation / Follow-up / Aftercare	
Transparency	
Assessment (Overall)	
(Assessment) Mechanism	
Assessment (Policy)	
(Assessment) Economic	
Fine-tuning of the programme	
Evaluation reports	

This report was funded by
the European Union's Internal Security Fund – Police